

Sono-photo-Fenton and photo-Fenton degradation of methylene blue : A comparative study

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Abstract : The oxidation using sono-photo-Fenton has been found to be a promising treatment for the effective decolorization and degradation of dye. The degradation of methylene blue was investigated using photo-Fenton and sono-photo-Fenton processes. The effect of different variables like the concentration of ferric ion, concentration of dye, pH, hydrogen peroxide, light intensity etc. on the reaction rate has been observed and optimal conditions determined. The methylene blue dye degradation was found to depend on these variables. The progress of dye degradation was observed spectrophotometrically. The sono-photo-Fenton reaction showed higher degradation rate of the dye as compared to photo-Fenton process. The results showed that the dye was completely oxidized and degraded into CO₂ and H₂O. A suitable tentative mechanism for degradation of methylene blue by sono-photo-Fenton's reaction has been proposed.

Keywords : Sono-photo-Fenton reagent, photo-Fenton reagent, ultrasonic irradiation, advanced oxidation process, sono-photochemical degradation, photochemical degradation, methylene blue.

Introduction

Water pollution by organic compounds is a major environmental concern throughout the world. Sonochemistry has emerged in past years as an advanced oxidation process for the destruction of hazardous organic compounds in aqueous solutions¹⁻⁵, but the sono-photochemistry is a new interdisciplinary field. Sonogenesis of hydroxyl radicals by ultrasonic sound can accelerate the course of chemical reactions. For the degradation of pollutants in aqueous solution, much attention has recently been focused on the so-called advanced oxidation processes for water and wastewater decontamination. In these processes, various techniques (e.g. photolysis, photocatalysis, Fenton reaction, sonochemistry, UV-H₂O₂, UV-O₃ and photo-Fenton) are applied to produce reactive species for inducing the transformation of water soluble organic or dye pollutants. This treated water may be used for some useful purposes like washing, cooling, irrigation and cleaning, which is not possible otherwise with polluted water.

Sonolysis of water yields hydroxyl radicals and hydrogen atoms. Hydroxyl radicals in particular are very reactive and can transform organic pollutants⁶⁻⁸.

Treatment method using the Fenton reaction⁹, utilizes hydroxyl radicals produced by interaction of H₂O₂ with ferrous salts.

In the dark, this reaction is stopped after complete conversion of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺ ions. The rate enhancement of degradation on light irradiation is due to photoreduction of Fe³⁺ ions back to Fe²⁺ ions, which produce new •OH radicals with H₂O according to the following mechanism¹⁰.

The direct photolysis of H_2O_2 also generates $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals.

In waste water treatment, the use of advanced oxidation processes (AOP's) has emerged during the last two decades, which involve the *in situ* generation of highly reactive hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$). The dark reaction of H_2O_2 with ferrous salts and the photo-assisted decomposition of H_2O_2 are possible sources of hydroxyl radicals for the destruction of organic pollutants¹¹⁻¹⁵. In the ultrasound-based chemical reaction systems, which are emerging as promising alternatives for the removal of refractory organics in treated effluents or natural waters has been reported by Ince *et al.*¹⁶ while Naffrechoux *et al.*¹⁷ reported the sonochemical and photochemical oxidation of organic matter like phenol. Decomposition of parathion in aqueous solution by ultrasonic irradiation has been reported by Kotronarou *et al.*¹⁸. Panwar *et al.*¹⁹ reported the sonochemical degradation of a triphenyl methane dye. Photo-Fenton reaction was used as an effective photochemical process to treat the polluted water by Ruppert *et al.*²⁰. The use of photo-Fenton's reagent for the photochemical bleaching of some dyes is also reported by Kumar *et al.*²¹⁻²³.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Methylene blue (Qualigen), FeCl_3 (CDH) and H_2O_2 (30%, Merck) were used. The concentrations of the solutions were 1.0×10^{-3} and 5.0×10^{-3} mol/L for methylene blue and FeCl_3 , respectively. These were used as stock solutions. Sono-photochemical degradation of methylene blue was investigated taking 30 mL of total reaction mixture consisting of dye solution, FeCl_3 solution and H_2O_2 . The concentration of dye is 1.66×10^{-4} mol/L for sono-photo-Fenton (SPF) and 2.0×10^{-4} mol/L for photo-Fenton (PF), of FeCl_3 is 5.0×10^{-4} mol/L for sono-photo-Fenton and 6.67×10^{-4} mol/L for photo-Fenton while H_2O_2 is 1.0 and 0.5 mL for sono-photo-Fenton and photo-Fenton, respectively, in the reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was exposed to the light (75.5 mW cm^{-2})

by using a 200 W tungsten lamp (Sylvania Laxman). The light intensity was measured with a Suryamapi (CEL Model SM 201). In sono-photo-Fenton reaction, the reaction mixture was also exposed to the ultrasound (Systronics Ultrasonic Cleaner-392, Italy), with frequency 40 KHz. A water filter was used to cut off thermal radiations. pH of the solution was adjusted by the addition of standardized sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions and measured with a digital pH meter (Systronics Model 335). The necessary condition for the correct measurement of absorbance is that the solution must be free from suspended particles. A G3 sintered glass crucible was used for filtration to obtain the desired accuracy in measurement of absorbance. λ_{max} of the dye was determined using an ultraviolet-visible spectrophotometer (Systronics Model 106).

Results and discussion

The photochemical degradation of methylene blue in presence of ultrasound was observed at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 635 \text{ nm}$. The structure of methylene blue has been given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Methylene blue : $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 635 \text{ nm}$.

The results of a typical run are represented in Table 1 and Fig. 2. It was observed that the absorbance of methylene blue solution decreases with increasing time of irradiation; thus, indicating that the dye is consumed. A plot of $\log(\text{Absorbance})$ against time was linear indicating that the reaction follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The rate constant k was calculated from the expression $k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$. The optimum rate constant for these reactions were determined as $k_1 = 1.69 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for photo-Fenton reaction and $k_2 = 3.07 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for sono-photo-Fenton reaction.

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the rate of degradation of methylene blue was investigated in the pH range 2.0 to 5.5. The results are reported in Table 2.

Table 1. A typical run

Time (min)	Photo-Fenton		Sono-photo-Fenton	
	Absorbance (A)	2 + log Absorbance (A)	Absorbance (A)	2 + log Absorbance (A)
0	0.860	1.934	0.825	1.916
2	0.686	1.836	0.582	1.765
4	0.569	1.747	0.408	1.611
6	0.460	1.663	0.275	1.439
8	0.398	1.600	0.198	1.297
10	0.320	1.505	0.140	1.146
12	0.255	1.407	0.098	0.991
14	0.208	1.318	0.065	0.813
16	0.167	1.223	0.045	0.653
18	0.139	1.143	0.036	0.556
20	0.116	1.064	0.023	0.362
22	0.091	0.959	0.016	0.204
24	0.076	0.881	0.011	0.041
26	0.062	0.792	-	-
28	0.050	0.699	-	-
30	0.039	0.590	-	-
32	0.033	0.519	-	-

$$k = 1.69 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

$$k = 3.07 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

The degradation of methylene blue depends strongly on pH of the reaction medium. The reaction rate increases with increasing pH up to 2.5 and 2.4 in photo-Fenton and sono-photo-Fenton reaction, respectively and then decreases. The hydroxyl radicals are generated in two steps;

- The reaction between Fe^{2+} ions with hydrogen peroxide, (i)
- Photochemical reaction of Fe^{3+} ions and water. (ii)

The increase in pH of the medium favors the step (i) where OH^- ions are formed along with hydroxyl radicals, whereas protons are generated in step (ii). Thus, it may be concluded that the step (i) dominates over step (ii) at pH below 2.4 and 2.5 in SPF and PF reaction, respectively. However, the retardation of the reaction

above pH 2.4 and 2.5 in SPF and PF reaction, respectively, suggests the dominance of step (ii) over step (i).

Effect of methylene blue concentration :

Effect of variation of dye concentration on the reaction rate was also studied by taking different concentrations of methylene blue solutions. The results are given in Table 3. The rate of degradation of the dye was found to increase with increasing concentration of methylene blue upto 1.66×10^{-4} mol/L and 2.00×10^{-4} mol/L in SPF and PF reaction, respectively. On further increasing its concentration, a sudden decrease in the rate of degradation was observed. On increasing the concentration above 1.66×10^{-4} mol/L and 2.00×10^{-4} mol/L in SPF and PF reaction, respectively, the reaction rate was found

Fig. 2. A typical run.

Table 2. Effect of pH

	Photo-Fenton	Sono-Photo-Fenton
[Methylene blue]	2.00×10^{-4} mol/L	1.66×10^{-4} mol/L
[Fe ³⁺]	6.67×10^{-4} mol/L	5.00×10^{-4} mol/L
H ₂ O ₂	1.5 mL	1.5 mL
Light intensity	75.5 mW cm^{-2}	75.5 mW cm^{-2}
		Frequency = 40 KHz

pH	Photo-Fenton $k \times 10^3 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	Sono-Photo-Fenton $k \times 10^3 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
2.0	0.54	1.46
2.1	0.52	1.68
2.2	0.84	2.00
2.3	1.00	2.42
2.4	1.30	3.07
2.5	1.69	2.78
2.6	1.38	2.34
2.7	1.13	2.00

Table 3. Effect of concentration of methylene blue

	Photo-Fenton	Sono-Photo-Fenton
pH	2.5	2.4
[Fe ³⁺]	6.67×10^{-4} mol/L	5.00×10^{-4} mol/L
H ₂ O ₂	1.5 mL	1.5 mL
Light intensity	75.5 mW cm^{-2}	75.5 mW cm^{-2}
		Frequency = 40 KHz

[Methylene blue] $\times 10^4$ (mol/L)	Photo-Fenton $k \times 10^3 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$	Sono-photo-Fenton $k \times 10^3 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$
0.33	0.43	0.89
0.67	0.54	1.50
1.00	0.79	2.04
1.33	1.00	2.47
1.66	1.23	3.07
2.00	1.69	2.30
2.33	1.39	1.54
2.67	1.18	1.18

to decrease. This may be attributed to the fact that as the concentration of methylene blue was increased, it may start acting as a filter for the incident light. The larger concentrations of dye methylene blue will not permit the desired light intensity to reach the dye molecules in the bulk of the solution.

Effect of ferric ion concentration :

The effect of concentration of Fe³⁺ ions on the rate of degradation of methylene blue was observed by keeping all other factors identical. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Effect of concentration of ferric ion

Photo-Fenton	Sono-Photo-Fenton	
[Methylene blue] = 2.00 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol/L	[Methylene blue] = 1.66 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol/L	
pH = 2.5	pH = 2.4	
H ₂ O ₂ = 1.5 mL	H ₂ O ₂ = 1.5 mL	
Light intensity = 75.5 mW cm ⁻²	Light intensity = 75.5 mW cm ⁻²	
	Frequency = 40 KHz	
[Fe ³⁺] × 10 ⁴ (mol/L)	Photo-Fenton k × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	Sono-photo-Fenton k × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)
0.83	0.14	0.43
1.67	0.24	1.08
2.50	0.55	1.84
3.33	0.81	2.40
4.17	1.03	2.83
5.00	1.37	3.07
5.83	1.50	2.28
6.67	1.69	1.74

It is clear from the data in the table that in both these cases; sono-photodegradation and photodegradation of the dye, the rate of degradation increases on increasing the concentration of Fe³⁺ ions up to 6.67 × 10⁻⁴ and 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol/L for PF and SPF, respectively. This may be explained on the basis that with the increase in Fe³⁺ concentration, there will be enhanced generation of •OH radicals and as a consequence, the rate of sono-photodegradation and photodegradation increases. However, on increasing the concentration of Fe³⁺ ions further (in sono-photodegradation), the rate of the reaction was found to decrease. This is because of the fact that Fe³⁺ ions imparts a yellow colour to the solution and at larger concentrations, it may also act as a filter for the incident light. As the concentration of Fe³⁺ was increased

above its optimum concentration, the rate of the reactions (6) and (7) become very fast. In reaction (6), hydroperoxyl radicals (•OOH) are generated, which consume more amounts of Fe³⁺ ions in PF but in SPF, an extra reaction (8) also consume Fe³⁺ ions and hence, Fe³⁺ ions are less available for reaction (5) and as a result, less •OH radicals are generated. Therefore, the rate of sono-photodegradation and photodegradation also decreases.

Effect of hydrogen peroxide :

The effect of the amount of hydrogen peroxide on the sono-photodegradation and photodegradation of methylene blue was also investigated. The results are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. Effect of amount of H₂O₂

Photo-Fenton	Sono-Photo-Fenton	
[Methylene blue] = 2.00 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol/L	[Methylene blue] = 1.66 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol/L	
pH = 2.5	pH = 2.4	
[Fe ³⁺] = 6.67 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol/L	[Fe ³⁺] = 5.00 × 10 ⁻⁴ mol/L	
Light intensity = 75.5 mW cm ⁻²	Light intensity = 75.5 mW cm ⁻²	
	Frequency = 40 KHz	
H ₂ O ₂ (mL)	Photo-Fenton k × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	Sono-photo-Fenton k × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)
0.5	1.25	2.68
1.0	1.41	2.83
1.5	1.69	3.07
2.0	1.23	2.41
2.5	0.97	1.82
3.0	0.71	1.63
3.5	0.68	1.23
4.0	0.57	1.04

It was observed that the reaction rate increases on increasing the amount of H₂O₂, attaining an optimum value of H₂O₂ at 1.5 mL for both reactions. Thereafter, the rate of degradation decreases on increasing the amount of hydrogen peroxide more than 1.5 mL for SPF and PF reactions. It is because of the fact that as the amount of H₂O₂ was increased above its optimum value (1.5 mL for both reactions), the rates of the reactions (9) and (10)

increase in PF system but in SPF system, an additional reaction (12) also increases the rate of reaction. From eq. (10), $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals are consumed rapidly due to more availability of H_2O_2 molecules. From eqs. (9) and (10), $\cdot\text{OOH}$ radicals are generated in more amounts. This $\cdot\text{OOH}$ radical is utilized in eq. (11) and H^+ ions are produced. As a consequence, the rate of sono-photodegradation and photodegradation decreases.

Effect of light intensity :

The effect of light intensity on the sono-photodegradation and photodegradation of methylene blue was also investigated. The results obtained are reported in Table 6.

Table 6. Effect of light intensity

	Photo-Fenton	Sono-Photo-Fenton
[Methylene blue] = 2.00×10^{-4} mol/L		[Methylene blue] = 1.66×10^{-4} mol/L
pH = 2.5		pH = 2.4
[Fe^{3+}] = 6.67×10^{-4} mol/L		[Fe^{3+}] = 5.00×10^{-4} mol/L
$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 1.5$ mL		$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 1.5$ mL
		Frequency = 40 KHz
Light intensity (mL)	Photo-Fenton $k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)	Sono-photo-Fenton $k \times 10^3$ (s ⁻¹)
27.7	0.45	2.19
30.6	0.68	2.27
34.6	0.79	2.33
39.6	0.84	2.51
45.6	0.99	2.64
53.2	1.17	2.83
62.9	1.41	2.85
75.5	1.69	3.07

Plots of the rate constant versus light intensity were linear, which indicate that an increase in the light intensity increases the reaction rate. This may be attributed to the increased number of photons reacting with Fe^{3+} ions and, as a result, increased numbers of active species, the hydroxyl radicals are formed. Therefore, an overall increase in the rate of reaction was observed.

Mechanism :

On the basis of experimental observations and the existing literature, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for sono-photodegradation of methylene blue with the sono-photo-Fenton (SPF) reagent.

By ultrasound :

An aqueous solution of ferric ions on exposure to light decomposes water into a proton and $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical and ferric ions are reduced to ferrous ions. The ferrous ions decompose H_2O_2 into hydroxide ion and hydroxyl radical, while these ions undergo oxidation to ferric ions. Due to reaction of ferric ions with H_2O_2 in presence of light, $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ radicals are also produced. The reaction of $\cdot\text{OH}$ with H_2O_2 also produces $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ radicals. Ferrous ions will undergo oxidation to ferric ions by addition of $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals, while ferric ions get reduced to ferrous ions by incorporation of $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ radical and producing H^+ ions. $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ radicals are highly unstable in water and undergo facile disproportionation rather than reacting slowly with dye molecules. The participation of hydroxyl radical as an active oxidizing species was confirmed by using a hydroxyl radical scavenger like propan-2-ol, where the rate of photodegradation was drastically reduced.

The $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals are consumed in five reactions. They can induce dissociation of H_2O_2 into $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ and water or they combine (dimerize) to form H_2O_2 molecules. They can also induce dissociation of $\text{HO}_2\cdot$ into water and O_2 . Secondly, these may react with methylene blue to give degradation products.

In SPF reaction, $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals are produced in two reactions. The ultrasonic radiations can induce dissociation of H_2O into $\bullet\text{OH}$ and $\text{H}\bullet$, and $\text{H}\bullet$ can induce dissociation of H_2O_2 into $\bullet\text{OH}$ and water, and this extra generation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals enhances the rate of SPF of reaction.

The main advantage of using sono-photo-Fenton's and/or photo-Fenton's reagents is the regeneration of the consumed Fe^{2+} ions on illumination. Each Fe^{2+} ion can produce many $\bullet\text{OH}$ radicals in contrast of the dark Fenton reaction. The process is a cyclic one, where as only a single $\bullet\text{OH}$ radical is formed from one ferrous ion in dark Fenton reaction. It means that the amount of ferrous salt required under SPF and PF conditions is very very small as compared to Fenton conditions, where ferrous ions are to be added at regular intervals; otherwise, the reaction will stop after complete conversion of ferrous ions to ferric ions. This is important from industrial point of view because further separation of ferric ions is not required after wastewater treatment²⁴⁻²⁹.

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